

SEVERAL NOTES ON JAKÓBCZYK'S HYPOTHESIS ON FERMAT NUMBERS

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Abstract

Over the past centuries, Fermat numbers have been studied by many authors with a number of notable results achieved. After a short historical introduction, the present article will concentrate on a hypothesis proposed by the Polish mathematician Jakóbczyk more than 70 years ago. The hypothesis will be viewed in a broader context of the sequences of generalized Fermat numbers.

—Dedicated to Professor Michal Křížek

1. Introduction

The famous Polish mathematician Franciszek Jakóbczyk (1905–1992) published in 1951 the following hypothesis not-yet resolved concerning the Fermat numbers.

Hypothesis 1. (Jakóbczyk, [3]). All Fermat numbers $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$ are square free.

For the original formulation of Hypothesis 1, see paper [3, p. 127]. Details of the life and work of Franciszek Jakóbczyk can be found in [6]. In 1730, the Swiss mathematician Christian Goldbach (1690–1764) proved, the following property of Fermat numbers.

Theorem 1. (Goldbach, 1730). *Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and let $m \neq n$. Then,*

$$\gcd(F_m, F_n) = 1. \tag{1}$$

Consequently, no two different Fermat numbers are divisible by a single prime.

For a proof of Equation (1) see [5, p. 33]. Should Hypothesis 1 be proven, together with Theorem 1, it would present a pair of remarkable and extraordinary beautiful mathematical statements.

Hypothesis 1 is closely related to another unsolved number theory problem related to Wieferich primes. Recall that an odd prime p is called a *Wieferich prime* if

$$2^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}. \tag{2}$$

The term of “Wieferich prime” was introduced in honor of the German mathematician Arthur Wieferich (1884–1954), who found a connection of primes p satisfying Equation (2) with the first case of Fermat last theorem. Wieferich [10] proved that, if p is an odd prime and $x^p + y^p + z^p = 0$ has a solution in integers x, y, z with $p \nmid xyz$, then $2^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$. So far only two Wieferich primes, 1093 and 3511, are known. Thanks to extensive calculations on a computer, it has been verified that, if the third Wieferich prime exists, then it must be greater than $2^{64} \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$. Whether the set \mathcal{W} of all Wieferich primes is finite or infinite is not yet known. The following implication was proved by Warren and Bray [9, p. 563].

Theorem 2. (Warren and Bray, 1967). *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 2$, and let p be an odd prime. If $p \mid F_n$, then $2^{(p-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{F_n}$.*

Theorem 2 can be extended as follows.

Theorem 3. *Let $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and let p be a prime. If $p \mid F_n$, then $p^2 \mid F_n$ if and only if $2^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$.*

For a proof of Theorem 3, see for example Krížek et al., [5, p. 68], and one may also refer to Ribenboim [7, p. 87]. The result presented in Theorem 3 provides the basic link between Hypothesis 1 and Wieferich primes.

In this paper, we will study Hypothesis 1 in a broader context of the sequences $\{F_n(a, b)\}_{n=0}^\infty$, where $F_n(a, b) = a^{b^n} + 1$, $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, and $a, b \geq 2$. First, we will find out for which sequences $\{F_n(a, b)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ Goldbach’s theorem can be generalized.

2. Basic Divisibility Properties of the Numbers $F_n(a, b)$

Proposition 1. *Let a, b, m, n be integers such that $2 < a, b$ and $0 \leq n \leq m$. Then the following three statements are true.*

- (i) *If $a \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ and $b \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then $\gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)) = 1$.*
- (ii) *If $a \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $b \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then $\gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)) = 2$.*
- (iii) *If $b \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then $\gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)) = F_n(a, b)$.*

Proof. Since $m > n$, there exists a positive integer k such that $m = n + k$ and we have

$$F_m(a, b) - 1 = a^{b^{n+k}} = (a^{b^n})^{b^k} = (F_n(a, b) - 1)^{b^k}. \tag{3}$$

We prove (i). Let us suppose that $\gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)) \neq 1$. Since $2 \nmid F_j(a, b)$ for every $j \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, there exists at least one odd prime p such that $p \mid F_m(a, b)$ and $p \mid F_n(a, b)$. Reducing modulo p , from (3) we obtain

$$-1 \equiv (-1)^{b^k} \pmod{p}.$$

Since b is even, this implies that p divides 2, which is a contradiction.

We prove (ii). If $j \in \mathbb{N}$, then,

$$F_j(a, b) = (a^{b^j} - 1) + 2 = (a - 1)(a^{b^j-1} + \dots + a + 1) + 2. \tag{4}$$

Now, as a is odd and b is even, we have

$$a - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ and } a^{b^j-1} + \dots + a + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}. \tag{5}$$

Next, it follows from Equations (4) and (5) that $F_j(a, b) \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. If $j = 0$, then $F_0(a, b) = a + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Hence,

$$2 \mid \gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)). \tag{6}$$

Let $p \neq 2$ be a prime satisfying $p \mid F_n(a, b)$. Then, $a^{b^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$. Since $2 \mid b$, we have $a^{b^{n+k}} \equiv (-1)^{b^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Hence, $F_{n+k}(a, b) \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$. Consequently, if $p \mid F_n(a, b)$, then $p \nmid F_m(a, b)$. This, together with Equation (6), yields $\gcd(F_m(a, b), F_n(a, b)) = 2$.

We prove (iii). Given that b is odd, we can write

$$F_{n+k}(a, b) = a^{b^{n+k}} + 1 = (a^{b^n} + 1)((a^{b^n})^{b^k-1} - (a^{b^n})^{b^k-2} + \dots - a^{b^n} + 1), \tag{7}$$

which implies $F_n(a, b) \mid F_{n+k}(a, b)$. This proves (iii). □

Let $\varphi_n(a, b)$ denote the number of prime factors of $F_n(a, b)$ including their multiplicities. The following Corollary 1 follows directly from part (iii) of Proposition 1.

Corollary 1. *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, b \geq 2$ and let $b \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then the sequence $\{\varphi_n(a, b)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is monotone increasing.*

Is the sequence $\{\varphi_n(2, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ monotone? This interesting question can be found in the book [5, p. 159, Problem 5]. By 2025, only the first twelve terms of the sequence $\{\varphi_n(2, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ have been found:

$$\{\varphi_n(2, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty = \{1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots\}.$$

In addition, it has been proven that $\varphi_{12}(2, 2) \geq 8$. Example 1 proves that, if $b \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then an analogue of Corollary 1 does not hold.

Example 1. (i) Let us consider the sequence $F_n(3, 2) = 3^{2^n} + 1$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_0(3, 2) &= 2^2, \\ F_1(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 5, \\ F_2(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 41, \\ F_3(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 17 \cdot 193, \\ F_4(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 21523361, \\ F_5(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 926510094425921, \\ F_6(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 1716841910146256242328924544641, \\ F_7(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 257 \cdot 275201 \cdot 138424618868737 \cdot 3913786281514524929 \cdot P_{21} \text{ and} \\ F_8(3, 2) &= 2 \cdot 12289 \cdot 8972801 \cdot 891206124520373602817 \cdot P_{90}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P_{21} &= 153849834853910661121, \\ P_{90} &= 707275264749309881405141965802671548079179711 \\ &\quad 820351316861777644606207216944972589404100097. \end{aligned}$$

From the above, we obtain $\{\varphi_n(3, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty = \{2, 2, 2, 3, 2, 2, 2, 6, 5, \dots\}$. Hence, the sequence $\{\varphi_n(3, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is not monotone.

(ii) Further, let us consider the sequence $F_n(46, 2) = 46^{2^n} + 1$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_0(46, 2) &= 47 \text{ is prime,} \\ F_1(46, 2) &= 29 \cdot 73, \\ F_2(46, 2) &= 4477457 \text{ is prime,} \\ F_3(46, 2) &= 17 \cdot 929 \cdot 1269398609, \\ F_4(46, 2) &= 97 \cdot 8513 \cdot 624737 \cdot 779065031672321, \\ F_5(46, 2) &= 257 \cdot 1569884896100468417 \cdot 400359077012692185282901663254593, \\ F_6(46, 2) &= 944257 \cdot 52208711297 \cdot 6806175851393423565671196264598472321 \cdot P_{53}, \\ F_7(46, 2) &= 8121089 \cdot 104782627167647104439041 \cdot P_{183}, \\ F_8(46, 2) &= 20305921 \cdot C_{419} \text{ and} \\ F_9(46, 2) &= P_{852} \text{ is prime,} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P_{53} &= 77761544048050719364650799308637798429621836404447873, \\ P_{183} &= 8000164224427963988366149921267918767006044470488209481743548 \\ &\quad 0184310308946237007187319721677041863694475922674939467714881 \\ &\quad 3429269468958663087375477941779802264336336491735777581466113. \end{aligned}$$

From the above, it follows that $\{\varphi_n(46, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty = \{1, 2, 1, 3, 4, 3, 4, 3, c, 1, \dots\}$, where $c = \varphi_8(46, 2) \geq 3$. This means that the sequence $\{\varphi_n(46, 2)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is not monotone.

In connection with [5, p. 159, Problem 5], presented in [5], we can formulate the following more general problem.

Problem 1. Prove or disprove the following statement. There are $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, where $a, b \geq 2$ and $b \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ such that the sequence $\{\varphi_n(a, b)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is monotone.

3. The Divisibility of $F_n(a, b)$ by the Square of a Prime

In 1997, Agoh, Dilcher, and Skula [1, pp. 30–31], introduced the concept of a Wieferich number with base a that substantially generalizes the concept of Wieferich prime as defined by Equation (2). For the purpose of the present article, it is sufficient to recall that a prime p is called a *Wieferich prime with base $a \in \mathbb{N}$, $a \geq 2$* if $p \nmid a$ and

$$q(a, p) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \text{ or equivalently, } a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}. \tag{8}$$

In Equation (8), $q(a, p) = (a^{\varphi(p)} - 1)/p$, where φ is the Euler function. For details see [1]. In the sequel, the set of all Wieferich primes with base a will be denoted by $\mathcal{W}(a)$. It will also be useful to recall the following definition. Let $a, m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 2$ and let $\gcd(a, m) = 1$. The smallest positive integer k for which $a^k \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$ is called the *multiplicative order* of a modulo m , written as $k = \text{ord}_m(a)$. A characterization of the set $\mathcal{W}(a)$ using the multiplicative order of a is provided by part (iii) of Lemma 1.

Lemma 1. *Let $a, h, m \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, m \geq 2$, and let $\gcd(a, m) = 1$. Further, let p be a prime such that $p \nmid a$. Then (i)–(iii) hold.*

- (i) $a^h \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$ if and only if $\text{ord}_m(a) \mid h$.
- (ii) $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) \in \{p \text{ord}_p(a), \text{ord}_p(a)\}$.
- (iii) $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ if and only if $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) = \text{ord}_p(a)$.

Part (i) of Lemma 1 can be found in the books [2, p. 148] and [8, p. 348]. For part (ii) and (iii), see [4, p. 4] and [4, p. 9], respectively.

Lemma 2. *Let $a, b, m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $a, b, m \geq 2$. If $a^{b^n} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{m}$, then $a^{b^t} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{m}$ for all $t \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$.*

Proof. Let us suppose that $a^{b^r} \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$ for some $r \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Since $r < n$, there exists an $s \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n = r + s$. It is clear that

$$a^{b^{r+s}} - 1 = (a^{b^r} - 1)((a^{b^r})^{b^s-1} + \dots + a^{b^r} + 1). \tag{9}$$

Reducing Equation (9) modulo m , we obtain $a^{b^{r+s}} \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$, which is a contradiction. \square

The following Theorem 4 provides a basic link between the square prime divisors of the numbers $F_n(a, b)$ and Wieferich primes with a base a .

Theorem 4. *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, b \geq 2$, $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, and let $p \neq 2$ be a prime such that $\gcd(ab, p) = 1$. Then (i) and (ii) hold.*

- (i) *If $p^2 \mid F_n(a, b)$, then $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and $\text{ord}_p(a) \mid 2b^n$.*
- (ii) *If $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and $\text{ord}_p(a) = 2b^n$, then $p^2 \mid F_n(a, b)$.*

Proof. We prove (i). Let $p^2 \mid a^{b^n} + 1$. Then $p^2 \mid (a^{b^n} + 1)(a^{b^n} - 1) = a^{2b^n} - 1$. This means that $a^{2b^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$. Hence, by part (i) of Lemma 3.1, we get

$$\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) \mid 2b^n. \tag{10}$$

Next, by part (ii) of Lemma 3.1, we have $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) \in \{p \text{ord}_p(a), \text{ord}_p(a)\}$. Let us suppose that $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) = p \text{ord}_p(a)$. Then by Equation (10), $p \text{ord}_p(a) \mid 2b^n$. Since $p \nmid b$, we find that $p = 2$, which is a contradiction. Hence, $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) = \text{ord}_p(a)$. By part (iii) of Lemma 3.1, we now obtain $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and, from Equation (10), we get $\text{ord}_p(a) \mid 2b^n$.

We prove (ii). Let $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and let $\text{ord}_p(a) = 2b^n$. Since $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$, applying part (iii) of Lemma 3.1, we get $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) = 2b^n$. Hence, by part (i) of Lemma 3.1, we have $a^{2b^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$ and, thus, $(a^{b^n} + 1)(a^{b^n} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$. Suppose now that $a^{b^n} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $a^{b^n} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Then we find $2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, which yields $p = 2$, a contradiction. Consequently, we have either $a^{b^n} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$ or $a^{b^n} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$. Suppose that $a^{b^n} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$. Then using part (i) of Lemma 3.1, we obtain $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) \mid b^n$, which is a contradiction with $\text{ord}_{p^2}(a) = 2b^n$. Hence, $a^{b^n} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}$, and the result follows. \square

Example 2 proves that the converse implications to the statements (i) and (ii) presented in Theorem 4 are not true.

Example 2. Let us consider the sequence $F_n(19, 6) = 19^{6^n} + 1$. For $n = 1$, we have $19^6 + 1 = 2 \cdot 13^2 \cdot 181 \cdot 769$. Hence, $13^2 \mid 19^6 + 1$. First, we show that the converse implication to part (i) of Theorem 4 is not true. Let $p = 7$. Then we have $\text{ord}_7(19) = \text{ord}_{7^2}(19) = 6$. Hence, $7 \in \mathcal{W}(19)$ and $6 = \text{ord}_7(19) \mid 2 \cdot 6$. However, from the equality $19^6 + 1 = 2 \cdot 13^2 \cdot 181 \cdot 769$, it follows that $7^2 \nmid 19^6 + 1$.

Further, let us consider the sequence $F_n(18, 6) = 18^{6^n} + 1$. For $n = 1$, we have $18^6 + 1 = 5^2 \cdot 13 \cdot 229 \cdot 457$. Hence, $5^2 \mid 18^6 + 1$. After some calculation, we get $\text{ord}_5(18) = \text{ord}_{5^2}(18) = 4$. Hence, $5 \in \mathcal{W}(18)$ and $4 = \text{ord}_5(18) \neq 2 \cdot 6$. This proves that the converse implication to part (ii) of Theorem 4 is not true.

If $b = 2$, Theorem 4 can be refined substantially.

Theorem 5. *Let $a \in \mathbb{N}$, $a \geq 2$, $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and let $p \neq 2$ be a prime such that $p \nmid a$. Then $p^2 \mid F_n(a, 2)$ if and only if $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and $\text{ord}_p(a) = 2^{n+1}$. Consequently, we have*

$$p^2 \mid F_n \text{ if and only if } p \in \mathcal{W} \text{ and } \text{ord}_p(2) = 2^{n+1}. \tag{11}$$

Proof. Let us assume that $p^2 \mid a^{2^n} + 1$. Then by part (i) of Theorem 4, $p \in \mathcal{W}(a)$ and $\text{ord}_p(a) \mid 2^{n+1}$. Because $p \mid a^{2^n} + 1$, we have $a^{2^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ and, applying Lemma 2, we find that $a^{2^t} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ for every $t \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Hence, $\text{ord}_p(a) \neq 2^t$ for every $t \in \{0, \dots, n\}$. This, together with $\text{ord}_p(a) \mid 2^{n+1}$, yields $\text{ord}_p(a) = 2^{n+1}$.

The converse implication follows immediately from part (ii) of Theorem 4. \square

Note that the assumption $p \neq 2$ in Theorem 5 cannot be omitted. See part (i) of Example 1. Here, we have $2^2 \mid F_0(3, 2)$ and $2 \notin \mathcal{W}(3)$.

Statement (11) has already been published, without a proof, in our recent paper [4, p. 19]. Let us now apply (11) to the known Wieferich primes 1093 and 3511. By direct calculation, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ord}_{1093}(2) &= \text{ord}_{1093^2}(2) = 364 = 2^2 \cdot 7 \cdot 13, \\ \text{ord}_{3511}(2) &= \text{ord}_{3511^2}(2) = 1755 = 3^3 \cdot 5 \cdot 13. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by (11), we obtain $1093^2 \nmid F_{1092}$ and $3511^2 \nmid F_{3510}$. Finally, note that Theorem 5 admits the possibility of \mathcal{W} being an infinite set, but no Wieferich prime p meets the condition $\text{ord}_p(2) = 2^k$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$. This fact makes Hypothesis 1 extremely interesting. An extension of Theorem 5 is provided by Theorem 6.

Theorem 6. *Let $a, D \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, D \geq 2$, $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and let $\text{gcd}(a, D) = 1$.*

(i) *If $2 \mid a$, then*

$$D \mid F_n(a, 2) \text{ if and only if } \text{ord}_D(a) = 2^{n+1}. \tag{12}$$

(ii) *If $2 \nmid a$, then (12) holds for every $D \neq 2$.*

Proof. Let us assume that $D \mid F_n(a, 2)$. Then $a^{2^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{D}$, which implies $a^{2^{n+1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{D}$. By part (i) of Lemma 1, we now obtain $\text{ord}_D(a) \mid 2^{n+1}$ and, by Lemma 2, we conclude that $\text{ord}_D(a) = 2^{n+1}$.

Conversely, assume that $\text{ord}_D(a) = 2^{n+1}$. Since $a^{2^{n+1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{D}$, we have

$$(a^{2^n} + 1)(a^{2^n} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{D}. \tag{13}$$

Let $d = \gcd(a^{2^n} + 1, a^{2^n} - 1)$. Then $a^{2^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{d}$ and $a^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{d}$, which implies $2 \equiv 0 \pmod{d}$. Hence, $d \mid 2$. This means that

$$\gcd(a^{2^n} + 1, a^{2^n} - 1) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } a \text{ even,} \\ 2 & \text{for } a \text{ odd.} \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

Let a be even. Combining Equations (13) and (14), we see that either

$$a^{2^n} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{D} \quad \text{or} \quad a^{2^n} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{D}. \tag{15}$$

Similarly, when a is odd, then it follows from Equations (13) and (14) that Equation (15) holds for every $D \neq 2$. Let us now suppose that $a^{2^n} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{D}$. Then by part (i) of Lemma 1, $\text{ord}_D(a) \mid 2^n$, which is a contradiction with $\text{ord}_D(a) = 2^{n+1}$. Now, it is clear from Equation (15) that $D \mid a^{2^n} + 1$, which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 7. *Let $a, b, D \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, b, D \geq 2$, and let $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Then (i) and (ii) hold.*

- (i) *If $2 \nmid b$ and $D \mid F_n(a, b)$, then $D \mid F_{n+k}(a, b)$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.*
- (ii) *If $2 \mid b$ and $D \mid F_n(a, b)$, then $D \nmid F_{n+k}(a, b)$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Proof. Let us assume that $D \mid a^{b^n} + 1$. Then $a^{b^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{D}$, which yields

$$a^{b^{n+k}} + 1 = (a^{b^n})^{b^k} + 1 \equiv (-1)^{b^k} + 1 \pmod{D}. \tag{16}$$

From Equation (16) now it follows that, if $2 \nmid b$, then $a^{b^{n+k}} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{D}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and, if $2 \mid b$, then $a^{b^{n+k}} + 1 \equiv 2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{D}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. This proves (i) and (ii). \square

The following definitions will be needed for the statement of Corollary 2. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, b \geq 2$ and let p be a prime. First, let us define the set

$$J(a, b, p^2) = \{n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} : p^2 \mid F_n(a, b)\}.$$

Next, if $J(a, b, p^2) \neq \emptyset$, we define the number $n_0 = n_0(a, b, p^2) \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ by

$$n_0 = \min J(a, b, p^2).$$

Corollary 2. *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $a, b \geq 2$ and let p be a prime. Next, let $J(a, b, p^2) \neq \emptyset$. Then (i) and (ii) hold.*

- (i) If $2 \nmid b$ and $p^2 \mid F_{n_0}(a, b)$, then the number n_0 is equal to the index of the first term of the period of the sequence $\{F_n(a, b) \bmod p^2\}_{n=0}^\infty$.
- (ii) If $2 \mid b$ and $p^2 \mid F_{n_0}(a, b)$, then the number n_0 is equal to the index of the last term of the pre-period of the sequence $\{F_n(a, b) \bmod p^2\}_{n=0}^\infty$.

Example 3 illustrates the difference between cases (i) and (ii) presented in Corollary 2.

Example 3. Let us consider the sequence $F_n(10, 3) = 10^{3^n} + 1$. Then we have $487^2 \mid 10^{3^5} + 1$. On the other hand, $487 \nmid F_n(10, 3)$ for every $n \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Applying part (i) of Theorem 7, we now obtain $487^2 \mid 10^{3^n} + 1$ for every $n \geq 5$. Hence, we have $n_0 = 5$ and, by direct calculation, we get

$$\{F_n(10, 3) \bmod 487^2\}_{n=0}^\infty = (11, 1001, 95497, 206448, 78154, 0, 0, 0, 0, \dots).$$

Further, let us consider the sequence $F_n(2968, 6) = 2968^{6^n} + 1$. Then we have $2593^2 \mid F_4(2968, 6) = 2968^{6^4} + 1$. Applying part (ii) of Theorem 7, we now find that $2593^2 \nmid F_n(2968, 6)$ for all $n \neq 4$. Hence, $n_0 = 4$ and direct calculation yields

$$\{F_n(2968, 6) \bmod 2593^2\}_{n=0}^\infty = (2969, 3331932, 3699454, 2884630, 0, 2, 2, 2, 2, \dots).$$

4. Paulo Ribenboim Revised

In the paper [7, p. 87], Paulo Ribenboim published the following short note: “Up to now, no number $a^{a^n} + 1$ with a square factor has ever been found.” In fact, if a is odd, then such numbers can easily be found. For example, for every $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} 3^2 \mid F_n(17, 17), & \quad 5^2 \mid F_n(49, 49), & \quad 7^2 \mid F_n(97, 97), \\ 11^2 \mid F_n(241, 241), & \quad 13^2 \mid F_n(337, 337), & \quad 17^2 \mid F_n(577, 577), \\ 19^2 \mid F_n(69, 69), & \quad 23^2 \mid F_n(803, 803), & \quad 29^2 \mid F_n(1681, 1681). \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

The relations $p^2 \mid F_n(a, a)$ listed in (17) immediately follow from part (i) of Theorem 7 after verifying that $p^2 \mid F_0(a, a)$. Other examples may be found in a similar way. If a is even, to find the square divisors of $F_n(a, a)$, part (i) of Theorem 4 can be used. Applying this result, the relations (18) can be found:

$$\begin{aligned} 17^2 \mid F_2(110, 110), & \quad 41^2 \mid F_2(834, 834), & \quad 73^2 \mid F_2(306, 306), \\ 97^2 \mid F_2(3234, 3234), & \quad 113^2 \mid F_2(1330, 1330), & \quad 193^2 \mid F_2(276, 276), \\ 257^2 \mid F_2(2964, 2964), & \quad 281^2 \mid F_2(1470, 1470), & \quad 577^2 \mid F_2(828, 828). \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

For an even a , we have also found numbers $F_n(a, a)$ each having a cubic factor. For example, if $a \in \{1022, 4514\}$, then $17^3 \mid F_2(a, a)$. Perhaps the most interesting example found is given in Equation (19).

$$17^3 \mid F_3(158, 158) = 158^{158^3} + 1. \tag{19}$$

Finally, let us note that, thanks to part (i) of Theorem 4, nontrivial examples can be found of the numbers $F_n(a, a)$ with an odd a each having a square factor. We can give some examples of the numbers $F_n(a, a)$ satisfying the relations $p \nmid F_0(a, a)$, $p \nmid F_1(a, a)$ and, $p^2 \mid F_2(a, a)$:

$$\begin{array}{lll} 19^2 \mid F_2(1743, 1743), & 37^2 \mid F_2(4407, 4407), & 127^2 \mid F_2(1155, 1155), \\ 163^2 \mid F_2(2547, 2547), & 251^2 \mid F_2(1295, 1295), & 677^2 \mid F_2(2899, 2899). \end{array}$$

5. Concluding Remark

The results presented indicate that, if Jakóbczyk’s hypothesis is true, then it describes a very special property of the Fermat numbers F_n that cannot be extended to the numbers $F_n(a, 2)$ that have a number of similar properties to F_n . Next, it is clear that resolving Jakóbczyk’s hypothesis will require fundamental new discoveries concerning the cardinality of the set \mathcal{W} .

Finally, if $\mathcal{W} = \{1093, 3511\}$ as conjectured by Nicolas Beeger, the discoverer of the second Wieferich prime, then every Fermat number is square free.

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